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Graphical Abstract

Nonlinear damping effects in vertically vibrating systems with violently sloshing liquid

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Abstract

Damping induced by vertically sloshing liquids at large amplitudes is of interest in the understanding of the dynamic response of aircraft wings containing fuel. This work presents the experimental investigation of sloshing-induced damping in two small rectangular tanks ($L = 100$ mm, $h = 37.5$ mm and 50 mm) under vertical excitation at various frequencies (3.3 to 10.3 Hz) and amplitudes (up to 1.57 tank heights). The focus is placed on large amplitudes that lead to violent vertical interactions between the liquid and the tank and the nonlinear damping effects they cause. The sloshing-induced dissipative energy in dimensional form shows a deviation from linearity with increasing amplitude of excitation, which is attributed to force-displacement hysteresis sub-cycle formations. When increasing the frequency of excitation, it is shown that the damping increases initially, and then remains constant. These findings are confirmed by a kinematics-based ballistic-harmonic model. Optical flow and a new technique based on pixel intensity standard deviation are employed in correlation with an analysis of the hysteresis cycles in order to offer insight into the sloshing force variation within one liquid cycle of oscillation.

Keywords: Damping, Hysteresis, Vertical Sloshing, Parametric Sloshing

1. Introduction

Liquid sloshing in the vertical direction has recently received much attention in the context of aircraft loads alleviation. Such efforts are currently being carried out as part of the EU-funded Horizon 2020, Airbus-led, project "Sloshing wing dynamics" (SLOWD), with the aim of increasing the effective damping in wings as a result of fluid-structure interaction. Several key results have been obtained thus far. It was shown in [1], both numerically and experimentally, that (1) the sloshing-induced damping due to vertical interaction between liquid and a vibrating tank is maximized at 50% filling level and (2) there is a sloshing-induced damping dependency on the amplitude of excitation, the induced damping ratio showing a maximum between 3 and 4g tank peak acceleration. These results were further confirmed in [2]. The authors experimentally showed in [3] the close correlation between the turbulence in the vertically-sloshing liquid and the dissipated energy. Reasoning based on liquid kinematics relative to the tank was shown to offer important insight into the influence of liquid movement patterns on sloshing-induced damping. This current work aims to further pursue the arguments presented in [3] while also expanding the parameter range

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3 experimentally achieved.
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7 In terms of amplitudes of excitation, from the point of view of sloshing-induced damping, there are three main
8 sloshing regimes that can be studied, which induce qualitatively and quantitatively different damping responses: (1)
9 low-amplitude damping in the linear regime, termed R2 in [1] due to it being the second regime occurring in time
10 in transient experiments, very well characterised classically (see [4] for a good synthesis); (2) mid-range amplitude
11 damping, highly nonlinear and termed R2&R1, where impacts with the tank ceiling start happening while influences
12 of sloshing modes are still visible (studied in [3]); (3) large amplitude damping termed R1, where the sloshing pattern
13 is determined solely by repeated violent impacts with the top and bottom of the tank (studied in [1, 2, 3]). The scope
14 of this work falls under the third category of large amplitude motions, with the main aim of experimentally character-
15 ising and explaining the induced damping trends.
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22 The parameters varied in this work are vertical vibration amplitude (presented as a quantity normalized to tank
23 height z/h) and frequency of excitation. A preliminary analysis can give us an indication of the amplitudes of oscillation
24 that an aircraft wing fuel tank can experience. For an aircraft with a wing aspect ratio of 10 typical of the Airbus
25 A320 family, the maximum tip deflection due to gusts can reach up to 2% of the wing span (around a static trim tip
26 deflection of approximately 4% of the span length) [5]. Considering a mean wing thickness of 11% of the chord and
27 a mean aerodynamic chord of 4.29 m [6], this would result in a tank thickness of 0.47 m. These values indicate that a
28 wing tank amplitude of $A/h \approx 1.5$ (amplitude normalized to tank height) can be expected. Of course, this normalized
29 amplitude value will vary in the span-wise direction as the wing deforms due to bending, but this analysis offers a
30 useful guide for further research. New and extended sloshing studies at amplitudes comparable with the tank height
31 are thus needed and motivate this work. In terms of experimental considerations, a larger tank than the one studied
32 in [1] is considered here in order to make sure that surface tension effects are reduced; there must also be found a
33 combination of the width and length of the tank such that, at lower amplitudes, the sloshing modes are well separated
34 in frequency. This combination of requirements, especially the large amplitudes in the vertical direction, is typically
35 limited by the test instrument operating envelopes. This current work therefore aims to provide extended experimental
36 study and refined analysis of the sloshing effects at high displacement amplitudes.
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47 This paper is organized as follows. A description of the experimental setup and methodology is offered in section 2.
48 Sloshing-induced damping characterisation in the frequency-amplitude domain is presented in section 3, followed by
49 an in-depth analysis of the kinematics-based results and the response loop hysteresis analysis.
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Figure 1: Experimental setup and test matrix

2. Methodology

The current study extends the work presented in [3] by considering two different tank heights and multiple frequencies of excitation as well as, very importantly, significantly increasing the achieved amplitudes of excitation. Figure 1 shows the experiment schematic and parameter space that was studied as part of this experimental campaign. Figures 1a and 1c show the schematic of the tank containing liquid and undergoing vertical excitation. Two different liquid-containing tanks were used, with the same length $L = 100$ mm and width $d = 30$ mm and different heights $h_1 = 50$ mm and $h_2 = 0.75h_1 = 37.5$ mm. The liquid column height is $h_w = 0.5h$, only one fill ratio being studied, and deionised water is used as the working liquid. The APS 113 ELECTRO-SEIS long stroke electrodynamic shaker (manufactured by APS Dynamics) is used to excite the system vertically. Designed to be used for calibration and evaluation of motion transducers, the APS shaker is suitable especially for low frequencies of excitation, optimized for measuring decay rates in lightly damped structures [7]. The peak-to-peak stroke distance is 158mm and the sine peak force is 133 N. The shaker works in a frequency range of DC-200 Hz. The forcing signal is sent to the power amplifier using a National Instruments USB-6211 Multifunction input/output device. Force and acceleration information is collected using a PCB 208C03 force sensor and a PCB 333M07 single axis accelerometer with a data sampling rate of 2048 Hz (all manufactured by PCB Piezotronics). The expected relevant frequency content to be observed in the sloshing system depends on the frequency of excitation, which is at a maximum of 10.3 Hz. Both force and acceleration signals are low-pass filtered at 30 Hz in order to ensure that no noise outside of the frequency range of interest is included in the signal. It was observed that filtering makes virtually no difference in the measured sloshing-induced damping, but slightly improves the quality of the force-displacement cycle representations.

For the given tank geometries, multiple sloshing modes can be present in the system, each with their own modal frequency given by [4]

$$\omega_{mn}^2 = \left(gk_{mn} + \frac{\sigma_w}{\rho_w} k_{mn}^3 \right) \tanh(k_{mn} h_w), \quad (1)$$

with $k_{mn} = \pi \sqrt{(m/L)^2 + (n/w)^2}$. Here, ω_{mn} is the natural angular frequency of sloshing mode (m,n) with mode shapes of m nodes in the x direction (tank-length-wise, see Figure 1a) and n nodes in the y direction (tank-width-wise). The gravitational acceleration is g , and σ_w and ρ_w are the surface tension and density of the working liquid. The first few sloshing frequencies are represented in Figure 2 for sloshing mode shapes (m,n) with up to three nodes in each direction. The x axis indicates the natural modes to which the frequencies on the y axis correspond. For example, there are three frequencies on column (m,0), corresponding to sloshing modes (1,0), (2,0) and (3,0). Note that the frequencies appear in pairs of 2 because of the (m,n) notation convention; also, the results for both tank heights are shown since there are small differences, especially at the lowest frequencies, driven by the change in the h_w parameter. Awareness of these modal properties of the liquid is important, since under parametric excitation, parametric instabilities arise, generating liquid response (Faraday waves) of sub-harmonic (at half the frequency of

Figure 2: First sloshing modes frequencies, 50% filling level, $L = 100$ mm, $d = 30$ mm, $h_1 = 50$ mm and $h_2 = 37.5$ mm

excitation), harmonic (at the frequency of excitation) or super-harmonic (when the excitation frequencies are multiples of the sloshing frequencies) [4]. Of these types of parametric resonances, the sub-harmonic type is usually observed experimentally. Note also that the focus in this work is on the rather large amplitudes generating vertical liquid slamming, and the low amplitude response generating linear or weakly-nonlinear waves is not studied here.

Force and acceleration information is collected at the interface between the shaker and the tank, which is forced vertically, for each experimental test case, using sinusoidal excitation at a single frequency and constant amplitude. Figure 1b shows a schematic of the test matrix in the frequency-amplitude domain. Each point represents a 60 seconds long test at the respective amplitude and frequency of excitation. The first 15 seconds are eliminated as they usually contain a transient response. After each individual test in Figure 1b, the experiment was stopped and the volume of liquid came to a standstill before starting the next experiment. The long-stroke shaker is limited in acceleration and displacement amplitude, and the structural integrity of the tank itself and its connection to the shaker are of concern when exciting it violently. Consequently, the experimental parameter space is limited in displacement amplitude and frequency, as is exemplified in Figure 1b. The test conditions are summarised in Table 1, where Fr is the Froude number, used here as a measure of nondimensional acceleration $Fr = \sqrt{A\omega^2/g}$, with g being the gravitational acceleration.

F	0.5
A/h	0 – 1.57
Fr	0 – 2.67
f [Hz]	3.3 – 10.3
h [mm]	37.5, 50.0

Table 1: Test conditions

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4 It is important to describe the particular way that the analysis is conducted in this work. After eliminating the
5 transient, all of the quantities discussed here are averaged over all of the tank cycles for each frequency-amplitude test
6 case. For example, considering that each test was 60 seconds long (of which the initial 15 seconds are eliminated),
7 this amounts to approximately 460 tank cycles at $f = 10.3$ Hz and 150 cycles at $f = 3.3$ Hz. Even after eliminating
8 hundreds of cycles of the initial transients, true steady-state response of the liquid is typically not achieved experi-
9 mentally. Considering the violent and heavily turbulent conditions of the interaction between the liquid and the tank
10 at large amplitudes, the sloshing force will not be the same in any two tank cycles; some variability will inevitably
11 appear, which is quantified using error bars throughout this work. Together with the mean value calculated based
12 on all cycles considered, error bars with $\pm 1\sigma$ standard deviation are included, showing the spread of the majority
13 of the data. More refined tools have been used in the past to study the spread of sloshing dissipation values under
14 violent vertical motion [8] but such analysis is out of the scope of this work. The force obtained from the sensor is
15 not used directly as a measure of the sloshing force, since it also contains inertial and gravitational components that
16 are independent of the sloshing liquid. The sloshing force is thus obtained by deducting the inertial components [3]
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$$24 \quad F_s = F - (m_w + m_s)a \quad (2)$$

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26 where F_s is the sloshing force, F is the total force measured by sensor, m_w is the mass of the liquid, m_s is the 'dry'
27 mass (i.e. mass of the tank and instrumentation) and a is the acceleration, as collected by the accelerometer underneath
28 the tank; the accelerometer used is piezoelectric, such that gravity is excluded from the collected acceleration signal.
29 Here, for consistency when correlating it with the liquid behaviour, the sign of the sloshing force follows the coordinate
30 system in 1a, positive when acting upwards. The experimental setup based on which these measurements are made is
31 presented in Figure 1d. It shows the tank containing liquid at the 50% filling level (1), the instrumentation (2,3) and
32 the long stroke actuator (4) exciting the system vertically.
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39 2.1. Statistical determination of liquid location

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41 One of the purposes of the study of a setup such as the one discussed in this work is to not only reveal dissipation
42 trends across multiple parameter variations but also to allow for in-depth analysis of what causes that dissipation
43 and how. In order to obtain insights into the link between the sloshing-induced damping at large amplitudes and the
44 behaviour of the liquid, a series of image processing techniques are used. Video footage recorded at 240 frames per
45 second was produced for the selected tests. This footage was further processed to indicate the position of the liquid
46 throughout an averaged tank cycle using statistical variations in pixel intensity; a similar procedure was first used
47 in [3] and, more broadly, pixel intensity statistics was also used for PIV (Particle Image Velocimetry) [9].
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52 Owing to the turbulent character of the investigated flows, the video analysis is performed on a computed averaged
53 fluid motion cycle. A fluid motion cycle corresponds generally to a tank motion cycle at large amplitudes of excitation.
54 At low amplitudes, due to the parametric excitation of the liquid (force of excitation is perpendicular to the free surface
55 of the liquid, generating Faraday waves) one fluid cycle corresponds to two tank cycles. The average location of the
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liquid across multiple fluid motion cycles is analysed and Figure 3 exemplifies the procedure used to determine the averaged location of the liquid across N cycles.

(a) Small amplitude sloshing example

(b) Large amplitude sloshing example

Figure 3: Illustration for computation of averaged liquid location for two sloshing regimes

Let us consider the same position of the tank in each cycle and let $I_k(n) \in (0, 1)$ be the intensity of pixel number k in liquid cycle number $n \in \{1, 2, \dots, N\}$ for the chosen position. Each video frame has 530×270 pixels. The pixel intensity has a value of 1 for a white pixel and 0 for a black pixel. Figure 3a shows a low-amplitude example where the position of the tank inside the cycle was chosen such that the liquid crest reaches a vertical maximum position relative

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3 to the tank. Two pixel positions are considered, I_1 close to the liquid crest and I_2 inside the relatively stationary body
4 of liquid. In this example, the liquid surface shows an instability where the wave crest moves left-right across multiple
5 cycles; the tank vertical mid-line is traced in Figure 3a to emphasize this effect. The liquid surface is not perfectly
6 two-dimensional but it deforms, the light passing through it creating contrasts that decrease the pixel intensity at the
7 liquid surface. Depending on the position of the wave crest, the value of I_1 varies considerably. By computing the
8 standard deviation of the intensity $\sigma(I_1)$ across N liquid cycles one can get an indication of the variability in liquid
9 surface position relative to the tank. The values of σ can be computed for all pixels and represented in a single image,
10 as shown in Figure 3a: blue shades correspond to lower and red ones to higher values of σ . In this example, due to
11 the wave crest position inconsistency across the N liquid cycles it can be seen that there is high value of σ at position
12 1. By contrast, at position 2, the light passing through the stationary body of liquid creates the same shade across
13 all cycles, leading to low standard deviations. In this example we see in only one picture a non-stationary effect that
14 could otherwise be observed only by studying the video footage. This type of analysis was first used in [3], where
15 multiple low amplitude examples are also shown.

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26 The large amplitude example shown in Figure 3b indicates another case where computing σ can be useful. For
27 this tank position inside the cycle, the liquid is found in the vicinity of the tank bottom. The surface of the liquid is
28 broken due to the turbulent character of the flow and, depending on the particular ways in which the liquid hits the
29 bottom of the tank, the surface can be found at different positions in different cycles. Consequently, for the case shown
30 in Figure 3b we again observe a lower standard deviation for the pixels close to relatively stationary bodies of liquid,
31 and higher values close to the moving surface. Even without the position of the surface changing, small-scale random
32 perturbations in the turbulent surface causes an increase in the statistical measures of image pixel intensity dispersion.
33 This type of analysis is used to indicate averaged movements of the liquid that are not seen in individual cycles and
34 are not easily observable by studying just the video footage.

35 36 37 38 39 40 41 2.2. Statistical determination of liquid velocity field

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43 Having thus an averaged location of the liquid relative to the tank, its averaged instantaneous velocity field can also
44 be calculated in order to obtain improved insight into the fluid kinematics; this is done based on the analysis of the dif-
45 ferences between the consecutive video frames. First, the tank motion is stabilized, effectively changing the reference
46 frame in the analysed videos from the global to local tank reference frame similar to the analysis in [10]. Then, *optical*
47 *flow* is used to determine the velocity field of the liquid relative to the tank. Optical flow is a two-dimensional velocity
48 field representative of the movement of brightness patches in an image [11]. The goal of optical flow is to include
49 time-varying information, namely object velocity, in stationary individual frames of a video. This technique has been
50 extensively used in computer vision with a comprehensive survey of its modern applications being presented in [12],
51 ranging from crowd motion estimation [13] and robot navigation [14] to weather prediction [15]. This technique has
52 been successfully applied in the past to highly aerated liquid flows, presenting however certain limitations. Most
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(a) Example of velocity field obtained using the Horn-Schunck method. Background: video frame; red arrows: velocity field; blue curves: streamlines

(b) Example of averaged velocity field. Background: standard deviation of pixel intensity; black arrows: velocity field; red curves: streamlines

Figure 4: Example of velocity field at an arbitrary tank position inside one cycle and averaged velocity field at the same position

notably, Arosquipa-Nina et al. [16] studied the free-surface self-aerated flow over a staircase-shaped configuration and showed that for void fractions (gas phase to liquid phase ratio) higher than 0.5, optical flow is not *quantitatively* representative of the liquid bulk velocity. Multiple methods of estimating the liquid velocity, when used together, can offer insights in a complementary fashion. However, this is true for horizontal flows where there is a noticeable, although highly aerated, liquid-gas interface. The approach taken in this work is thus to average the optical flow results over multiple similar tank cycles in order to indicate persistent liquid movement trends; this is especially useful in experimental configurations such as the one considered here, where numerous similar oscillation cycles are available for analysis. Because of these limitations and uncertainties, where quantitative data is shown in this present work (such as the averaged liquid bulk velocity), the numbers should be interpreted as to indicate liquid behaviour relative to other parts of the average tank cycle, and not in an absolute fashion or as indicative of calibrated flow measurements.

In the current experimental setup, light is diffused on a screen behind the tank, creating powerful contrasts between the moving liquid and the background, ideally suited for the optical flow-based tracking of brightness patches. The Horn-Schunck method [11] was used as implemented in ‘estimateFlow’ in MATLAB R2021a. Figure 4 shows an example of a velocity field obtained using this method. Figure 4a shows the velocity field at one instant of time inside a tank cycle, where the liquid is found close to the bottom of the tank. Red arrows show the velocity field computed using the current (shown) and the previous video frames. The turbulent liquid surface creates contrasting patches with the background, whose change from one frame to the next is used to determine the velocity of each such patch. While some instantaneous tendency of the liquid motion can be observed this way especially with the aid of the blue flow streamlines, it can be better appreciated by taking a statistical approach. Figure 4b shows the velocity field for the same position of the tank as in Figure 4a, this time averaged over multiple liquid motion cycles. The background shows the pixel intensity standard deviation obtained using the methodology discussed in Section 2.1. The black arrows represent the average velocity at each chosen pixel (arbitrary seeding was used) and the flow streamlines are represented with red curves. The liquid’s tendency of motion is clearly visible this way and, for instance, the

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3 formation of two counter-rotating bodies of liquid is revealed in this case, consistent with what was observed in the
4 video footage. This type of insight could not be obtained and represented otherwise but in this statistical manner,
5 thus showing the advantage of using this method for the current analysis. Notably, a modified PIV procedure called
6 bubble image velocimetry (BIV) has also been used in the past to study velocity fields in impacting sloshing problems
7 (e.g. [17, 18]).
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12 Finally, considering that the vertical dynamics of the sloshing system is of interest in this current work, the ver-
13 tical projections of all of the velocity vectors in Figure 4a can be averaged, giving a qualitative indication of the
14 instantaneous tendency of motion of the entire quantity of liquid relative to the tank, as well as a quantitative av-
15 eraged vertical velocity – referred to as *averaged liquid bulk velocity* (v_m^z) in this work. This information can be
16 used in correlation with other quantities (such as tank displacement) in order to offer further insight into the vertical
17 fluid-structure interaction, by indicating the overall tendency of motion of the entire body of liquid relative to the tank.
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21 Together with the displacement and velocity of the tank obtained from the acceleration data, there is thus a com-
22 prehensive kinematic description of the experimental sloshing system made available.
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25 26 27 28 **3. Results**

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30 Based on the experimental setup and methodology described in section 2, a series of results is presented. The
31 aim is to develop insight into the dissipative mechanisms and phenomena occurring in vertical sloshing, as well as
32 experimental and numerical justification for the trends observed. An overall view of the damping map over the entire
33 frequency-amplitude domain is presented in section 3.1 and then the ballistic-harmonic model analysis of the same
34 phenomena is given in section 3.2. The analysis is then followed by a detailed presentation of the liquid behaviour
35 through the forces exerted on the vibrating tank and their statistical behaviour in section 3.3.
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38 39 40 41 *3.1. Frequency-amplitude characterisation of sloshing induced damping*

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43 The sloshing force-displacement cycles are hysteretic by nature. The area enclosed by these cycles determines
44 the amount of energy that is dissipated from the forced fluid-structure system due to the action of the liquid during a
45 single response cycle. Similar investigations were previously conducted for lower amplitudes under vertical harmonic
46 excitation [3], as well as for lateral excitation [19].
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50 The sloshing induced energy dissipation discussed in this section is based on numerical integration of the identified
51 sloshing force with respect to the measured tank displacement (trapezoidal rule integration of the sloshing force vector
52 with respect to the tank displacement vector). To reveal the dominant and persistent response patterns, we take a
53 statistical approach by calculating the averaged hysteretic cycles. These are obtained as the arithmetic means of the
54 recorded consecutive force-displacement cycles. Because of the length of the overall acquisition time per each test
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Figure 5: An example of the averaged sloshing force-displacement cycle, $f = 8.3$ Hz, $A/h = 0.42$

case, typically, this amounts to the sample sets consisting of hundreds of cycles. Moreover, it is also useful to assess the cross-cycle variation in the sloshing force. Considering the violent nature of the vertical interaction between the liquid and the tank, the liquid is not expected to provide exactly periodically repeating sloshing forces across the successive cycles. The averaging process is therefore used to provide a robust indication of the interactional patterns. Figure 5 shows an example of such a hysteresis cycle for the case with frequency $f = 8.3$ Hz and tank amplitude $A/h = 0.42$. The mean force values are shown and, to illustrate the cross-cycle variance and extreme values, the curves representing the $\pm 1\sigma$ standard deviation bounds and the minimum and maximum force values for each tank position are also included. The variation in the sloshing force stems from variations in the sloshing behaviour, as well as errors in the measurements. With reference to Figure 5, it is noteworthy that the variability in the sloshing force is maximized around the points of maximum and minimum z/h values where the liquid impacts the top and bottom of the tank. Non-uniformity in the impacting interaction leads to non-uniformity in the observed sloshing forces. The dissipative energy was calculated using this procedure for each of the points of the test matrix shown in Figure 1b and Table 1, such that the variation of sloshing-induced damping can be analysed across the entire frequency and amplitude range. After discussing the observed global damping trends, an analysis of the mean hysteresis cycles will be presented in Section 3.3.

Figure 6 shows both the dimensional and normalized (to the liquid mass, frequency and amplitude of excitation) mean energy dissipated per cycle and its standard deviation as a function of the tank amplitude divided by its height (A/h), for three different frequencies of excitation. The normalized energy dissipated per cycle is written as

$$E_c = \frac{E}{m_w \omega^2 A^2} \quad (3)$$

where E is the dimensional mean energy dissipated per cycle, m_w is the liquid mass, ω is the frequency of excitation and A is the amplitude of excitation.

Damping data obtained from the harmonic excitation experiments were previously presented [3] as a function of

Figure 6: Variation of the energy dissipation per cycle for tank height $h = 37.5\text{mm}$ and three frequencies of excitation. Experimental data shown using markers with standard deviation bars. Analytic functions are fitted to the experimental data (blue and red dashed curves), showing amplitude-asymptotic similarity in the non-dimensional form.

Froude number. However, Fr is a normalized acceleration where the magnitude of the acceleration is $a = A\omega^2$ and so when studying different frequencies of excitation, the meaning of the E_c variation with amplitude of excitation may be obscured by placing too much emphasis on the frequency. The experimental data presented in Figure 6b in normalized form shows significant mutual overlap for the three frequencies shown, when represented as a function of A/h . Figure 6a shows the same data in the dimensional form. For all frequencies shown, the energy dissipated per cycle shows near-parabolic variation with positive curvature (convex) roughly corresponding to region R2&R1 (combination of a sloshing mode and significant interaction with the tank ceiling) and negative curvature (concave) in R1 region, corresponding to purely vertical and violent sloshing of the liquid. Approximating quadratic functions have been fitted over the data ($R^2 \geq 0.99$ for all curves shown) and, when displayed in their nondimensional form, they display substantial overlap in region R1 (Figure 6b).

While the variation of E_c in its nondimensional form shows a decaying trend with amplitude, it is not immediately obvious why a deviation from linearity in the *dimensional* $E(A/h)$ occurs at large amplitudes. A detailed analysis of the measured hysteresis cycles performed in Section 3.3 is necessary to explain this phenomenon because the large amplitude behaviour is the focus of this work. Along with this, the asymptotic behaviour of the sloshing system at large values of A/h will be also investigated.

A quadratic polynomial model is used to fit the data. This regression model is used for all measured excitation

Figure 7: Large amplitude (R1) parabolic fit coefficients versus frequency of excitation. Dashed curves correspond to the right-hand-side axis, and vertical dashed gray lines indicate sloshing frequencies.

frequency cases. The polynomials are functions of the normalized amplitude A/h

$$y = \sum_{k=0}^2 a_k (A/h)^k \quad (4)$$

where a_k are the coefficients obtained by least squares fitting. The fitted parameters for the excitation frequency range 4.3-10.3 Hz are presented in Figure 7 on the left hand side axis (solid lines). On the right hand side axis there are the same coefficients, divided by the square of the frequency of excitation (dashed curves). For reference, the sloshing frequencies and their multiples are shown as well using the vertical dashed lines, corresponding to the data shown in Figure 2 for the $h = 37.5$ mm tank. The sloshing frequencies are shown here for completeness; they drive the sloshing patterns at low amplitudes of excitation (in the linear sloshing domain), and are thus unlikely to have a significant influence on the large amplitude of excitation regimes.

It can be seen that there are larger values for the linear term and a quadratic term complements well the regression model chosen in this study. The fact that the coefficients (especially the linear coefficient a_1), when divided by the frequency squared, show little variation in this excitation frequency range indicates that, at large amplitudes, the normalized energy dissipated per cycle is largely independent of the excitation frequency (remember that $E_c(\omega) = 1/\omega^2 \cdot E/(m_w A^2)$).

For the case discussed in this paper, a regression model that is able to predict the dissipative energy for the frequency range of 5.3 - 10.3 Hz, at large amplitudes is

$$E_c = -\frac{10^{-5}}{m_w A^2} (1.118 - 7.665(A/h) + 2.253(A/h)^2) \quad (5)$$

The coefficients for this model were obtained by averaging the ω^2 -normalized values presented in Figure 7, with

units of kg m^2 . The corresponding curve is sketched in Figure 6b in red. This large-amplitude behaviour was observed to be true for the frequencies between 5.3 and 10.3 Hz for this setup; it is not clear if a nondimensional frequency threshold exists and, if so, what that threshold is. This model is good for the frequency range in which data was available and in which the regression analysis was completed. At lower frequencies, the ω^2 -normalized dominant coefficient a_1 shown in Figure 7 shows a significant deviation from the constant trend established by the other frequency values, suggesting at values lower than 5.3 Hz there is a stronger dependency of E_c on frequency.

The trends identified above are important because it can be shown [3], based on the damped single degree of freedom oscillator theory, that

$$E_c = -\frac{1}{2} \frac{M}{m_w} (1 + \zeta^2) (e^{-4\pi\zeta} - 1) \quad (6)$$

where ζ is the equivalent system damping ratio. Note that E_c is nominally negative, representing a dissipative energy, but the results are shown here with a positive sign, consistent with the conventions used previously. Using the approximation $\zeta^2 \rightarrow 0$ we have

$$\zeta \approx -\frac{1}{4\pi} \log \left(1 - 2E_c \frac{m_w}{M} \right) \quad (7)$$

Assuming constant damping ratio and single degree of freedom behaviour, the results presented here extend to transient free vibration cases in a straightforward manner. This in turn is important, since it means that the conclusions drawn here can be extended to more complex sloshing cases where the dynamical behaviour is still dominated by a single frequency and can thus be approximated by a single degree of freedom system.

Similar parametric dependencies of sloshing-induced dissipation were studied by the authors in the past. In Figure 11 from [1] a variation of damping ratio due to vertical sloshing in a transient experiment was shown, as a function of excitation acceleration amplitude and time. Based on an analytical model that will also be employed in this work, the variation of induced damping with the Froude number and inverse excitation amplitude was shown in Figure 21 in [3]. The Froude number contains information about excitation acceleration ($\omega^2 A$), so indirectly about excitation frequency and amplitude. A natural extension of this analysis in the context of this paper is then given by the representation of the curves shown in Figure 6 as dissipation maps spanning different amplitudes and frequencies of excitation, as shown in Figure 8. Such maps, albeit more limited in amplitude, were also shown in [20]. In the case presented here, cubic spline smoothing was performed on the mean energy values at each amplitude, using the Matlab R2021a implementation under the function 'csaps'. Linear interpolation was used with the resulting curves in order to create a surface over the 2D frequency-amplitude domain. The experimental data points are presented as red markers, corresponding with the scheme shown in Figure 1b. We should emphasize that the surface interpolation is done for visualisation and comparison purposes only and experimental data is known only at the specified points marked with red dots. The frequency resolution of 1 Hz means that experimental data is not available between the black curves

Figure 8: Energy dissipation per cycle as function of the frequency and amplitude of excitation, two tank heights (a) $h = 37.5$ mm and (b) $h = 50.0$ mm. Red markers: experimental data points

in Figure 8. This analysis was conducted for both tank heights and is shown in Figure 8a for $h = 37.5$ mm and in Figure 8b for $h = 50$ mm. As in Figure 7, the frequencies corresponding to the 2-dimensional and 3-dimensional sloshing modes in the frequency range studied here are shown as well, for the two tank heights. Multiple sloshing modes were indeed observed experimentally, excited either via the 1:1 resonance condition, such as the mode (2,0) being observed in the 3.3 Hz case, or parametrically with the 2:1 excitation-to-response frequency ratio, as in the 7-8 Hz range with mode (2,0) or in the 10.3 Hz case with mode (3,0). Such sloshing modes dominate the system's dynamic response only for the first one or two amplitudes in each case in Figure 8, and at larger amplitudes the response is vertical impact-driven.

There are multiple ways the surfaces in Figure 8 can be interpreted. The E_c values are colour-coded with a maximum achieved at $E_c = 1.5$. The horizontal axis shows the different frequencies analysed (3.3 – 10.3 Hz) and the vertical axis shows the tank amplitude normalized to tank height. Data on the upper right hand side is not available experimentally, as this region requires both very high frequencies and amplitudes, not achievable experimentally at the same time. The experimental data for both tank heights are shown here, to emphasize the differences that were found. Note that for the $h = 50$ mm case, due to the larger value of the tank height, the experimentally achievable A/h ratio was limited to 1.1. There is a very good level of agreement between the experimental cases across the entire energy range. The main differences are found at higher E_c values (1.3 to 1.5), where the $h = 50$ mm experimental case predicts a wider energy plateau in terms of frequencies and a slightly higher maximum E_c value. These differences may arise from (1) experimental uncertainties (only mean E_c values are used here), (2) differences in the measurement

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3 point availability and consequently surface fitting and (3) varying sloshing pattern influences due to change of the tank
4 height. However, these differences are not deemed to be substantial.
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6 This map is effectively bounded by the achievable acceleration amplitude, which was approximately $7.1g$ ($Fr =$
7 2.67); this represents a substantial improvement over what is usually achieved experimentally in vertical sinusoidal
8 excitation. Moving from 0 to the maximum achieved amplitudes in Figure 8, it can be seen that E_c shows an initial
9 increase up to a maximum value, after which it drops. This increase and then drop in E_c vs A is observed across all
10 frequencies. The existence of a maximum nondimensional dissipation was in the past correlated with the change of
11 sign of the phase angle between tank velocity and sloshing force [3], indicative of a change in the timing between
12 sloshing impacts and tank position. These changes in liquid/ tank phasing are further explored here in Section 3.3
13 in terms of sloshing force - tank displacement hysteresis cycles. Past the point of maximum dissipative energy, even
14 though the dimensional energy keeps increasing, the nondimensional E_c shows a decreasing trend. This is conse-
15 quence of normalization of E_c to the square of the amplitude and was previously observed in particle impact damping
16 as well [21]. Moving from left to right, from the lowest frequency to the maximum of 10.3 Hz, it is seen that E_c shows
17 an increase and then it plateaus. This variation is consistent with the variation of the frequency-normalized fitted
18 parameters shown in Figure 7. From a fundamental perspective, the observed variation of sloshing-induced energy
19 dissipation E_c with excitation amplitude and frequency is significant, since it indicates somewhat counterintuitively
20 that as the amplitude of excitation is increased past a certain value, there is no additional dissipation due to vertical
21 sloshing. Moreover, at a constant amplitude of excitation, increasing the frequency does not substantially increase the
22 dissipation, even though the excitation acceleration is increased.
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24 Multiple approaches can be taken to interpret the obtained results, e.g. those observed at a single frequency of the
25 excitation. For instance, [1] considered the dynamic interaction between an equivalent mechanical model represented
26 by a bouncing ball and a vibrating tank via a coefficient of restitution. We further explore this kinematic reasoning
27 which employs a ballistic-harmonic model to study the present extended experimental model.
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30 31 32 33 34 35 36 37 38 39 40 41 *3.2. Kinematics-based prediction of dissipative trends: the B-H model*

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44 Similar damping trends to those presented in Figure 6 have been observed, at large amplitudes and a single
45 frequency of excitation, in vibrating beam experiments in particle impact damping. Already Friend & Kinra [21] have
46 shown that an analytical model based on a coefficient of restitution can be used to describe the vertical interaction
47 between granular materials and a vibrating beam. A similar analytical model was used to describe sloshing in a single
48 degree of freedom coupled fluid-structure system [1]. Considering the qualitatively similar large-amplitude damping
49 trends, as well as the fact that both liquid and particle systems can be described by a similar reduced order models,
50 there is strong indication that, at large amplitudes, the two systems share energy dissipation properties that transcend
51 the liquid-specific qualities. It is known that the dynamics of the problem is important: the sloshing force is the driver
52 of sloshing-induced damping across all amplitudes of excitation and, especially at low amplitudes, the liquid sloshing
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3 dynamics in the absence of interaction with the roof of the tank is the root cause of damping. However, at larger
4 amplitudes, we believe that the kinematics of the relative liquid-tank motion is more important in the variation of
5 induced damping.
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8 We hypothesise that at large Froude numbers the kinematics of the problem, i.e. the liquid-tank impact velocity
9 and the number of liquid-tank roof or bottom impacts in one cycle, is determinant for the amount of the sloshing-
10 induced dissipated energy and any chosen descriptive measure of it. In order to test this hypothesis, we employ the
11 use of a kinematics-based ballistic-harmonic model (B-H model). For a full description of the model, see [3]. The
12 model is purely based on the kinematics of the motion of a fluid-equivalent particle inside a vertically and sinusoidally
13 oscillating tank, approach justified by the observed bulk motion of the liquid at large amplitudes of excitation. If the
14 acceleration of the tank exceeds 1g threshold, the ball will leave the bottom of the tank and enter a ballistic trajectory.
15 During this free-flight stage, there is no dynamic interaction between the particle and the tank. Rather, a dissipative
16 energy per cycle can be calculated by assuming that the whole energy of the ball is transferred to the tank when it hits
17 either the bottom or the top. However, in the real liquid-structure interactional context, it is not rational to assume that
18 the entirety of the liquid mass interacts with the tank at a single impact instant and that the entire kinetic energy is
19 transferred at once. A kinematics-based model will thus generally over-predict the dissipated energy. To reflect on this
20 and for the sake of dimensional comparison with the sloshing case, we introduce a correction factor for the interacting
21 liquid mass and assume that, instead of the whole liquid mass interacting with the tank walls when intersections
22 between the ballistic and the harmonic trajectories occur, only a fraction α of the mass transfers its kinetic energy. We
23 can thus effectively determine the nondimensional dissipative energy per cycle in the B-H model with the correction
24 factor applied
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$$E_c = \frac{1}{2} \alpha \frac{v_{rel}^2}{\omega^2 A^2} \quad (8)$$

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36 where α is the fraction of mass transferring its kinetic energy to the tank and v_{rel} is the relative velocity between
37 the particle and the tank. The fraction of mass α is thus the only parameter that was chosen at $\alpha = 0.48$ such that
38 the maximum dissipated energy per cycle within the amplitude and frequency range presented here is the same as
39 the experimentally-measured value. Similar approaches have been taken in less violent, classical sloshing motion
40 context; for example, Ruiz et al. [22] used an ‘efficiency index’ to account for the fraction of liquid mass that does not
41 contribute to the sloshing mode studied.
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48 Figure 9 shows the dissipation trends computed by the B-H model, as well as a comparison with the experimental
49 results for the $h = 37.5$ mm case. Figure 9a shows the E_c map as a function of frequency and amplitude of the
50 tank. The kinematics-based model estimates in Figure 9a support the interpretation of the experimentally identified
51 *dissipation trends*. The fact that this type of model is capable to predict the E_c trends to a good degree is indicative
52 of the fact that, at large Fr numbers, it is not the liquid-specific behaviour that explains the sloshing-induced energy
53 dissipation. **The sloshing mode frequencies are only shown here in Figure 9b, since the B-H model cannot model any**
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Figure 9: Ballistic-harmonic model prediction of dissipation trends and comparison with experimental data, $h = 37.5$ mm

low-amplitude, non-impacting sloshing phenomena.

In order to support this analysis, Figure 9b shows the interpolated surface from Figure 8a and the corresponding experimental maximums E_c (red square markers). In the same figure there is also shown the B-H prediction for the maximum E_c values (grey curve) and the curve above which there are intersections with both ceiling and bottom of the tank (dashed gray curve). As the acceleration of the tank increases, it imparts to the ball a high enough energy such that it hits both the ceiling as it goes up, and the bottom of the tank as it comes back down, both within one single tank cycle. As shown in [3], this is also the reason why a cusp appears in Figure 9b close to the maximum E_c values. Considering that the dissipative energy in the B-H model is directly determined from the hits between the ball and the tank, multiple hits within one cycle increases the dissipative energy per cycle. From a computational perspective, unfortunately, even for a simple kinematics model such as the B-H model the ball-tank intersection conditions cannot be determined analytically, as it leads to a transcendental equation of the type $x^2 + x = \sin(x)$. The grey curves presented in Figure 9b have thus been computed numerically according to the scheme presented in [3].

The experimental maximums of E_c in Figure 9b at the lower frequencies (i.e. 3.3 Hz and 4.3 Hz) are determined with lower confidence due to the comparatively smaller number of data points that are available for the lower frequency range and the corresponding extended amplitude range (see the spacing between the red points in Figure 8). However, it can be seen that the experimental data generally follow closely the trend established by the B-H model: the dissipative energy is maximized in the vicinity of the region where the kinematic conditions are met such that the liquid can impact both the top and the bottom of the tank twice per single tank oscillation cycle. This conclusion is important because it provides additional support to the idea that the lumped liquid behaviour is the determinant for

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3 the amount of energy that is dissipated following the vertical interaction with the tank. Specifically, the kinematic
4 condition is related to the initial velocity that must be imparted to the liquid and causing it to enter a ballistic tra-
5 jectory inside the tank such that two impacts with the tank per one cycle are possible. However, owing to the fact
6 that liquid is a distributed medium, in reality, there are various other contributing phenomena such as surface tension
7 and internal cohesion forces. None of these are included in the current basic model. Furthermore, in contrast with a
8 simple kinematics-based model behaviour, the mass of the liquid does not interact with the tank in an instantaneous
9 and uniform fashion. In reality, the interactional events such as impacts are distributed throughout the test cycle. In
10 order to develop the general understanding of the impact events further, including their temporal distribution inside a
11 full motion cycle and the influence on the resulting dissipative energy, an in-depth force-displacement cycle analysis
12 is conducted next.

13 3.3. *Hysteretic response cycle analysis across the averaged liquid behaviour*

14 Let us now focus our attention to the changes in the shape of the hysteresis cycles emerging with the increasing
15 amplitude and frequency. Figure 10 summarises the mean force-displacement loops for the selected A/h values and all
16 frequencies available. Due to the experimental limitations (limited shaker power output and, consequently, the peak
17 accelerations too), as the A/h value is increased the maximum achievable frequency is reduced; this aspect can best
18 be appreciated by looking at the envelope encompassing the surfaces in Figure 8. As we move to larger amplitudes in
19 Figure 10, the shape and size of the cycles gradually change as well. An important observation is that the qualitative
20 attributes of the shapes of the cycles are shown here to depend mainly on the normalized amplitude rather than another
21 parameter (e.g. Froude number). Further, the shapes are mutually similar at the higher frequencies for the same A/h
22 value, which is consistent with the damping values seen in the corresponding regions in Figure 8. The explanation for
23 this similarity can be drawn from the kinematics-based arguments. Throughout all of the cases shown in Figure 10,
24 the sloshing force has peaks in the vicinity of the minimum and maximum z/h values (bottom-most and top-most
25 positions of the tank inside one cycle of oscillation). The first quadrant's peak corresponds to the impacts between
26 the liquid and the top of the tank, while the third quadrant's peak is due to the impacts with the bottom of the tank.
27 The sloshing force peaks are absent at lower amplitudes and frequencies because the acceleration (or deceleration) of
28 the tank is not sufficient to either eject the liquid onto the ballistic trajectory or to introduce the conditions leading to
29 noticeable impact with the tank top.

30 At very large amplitudes ($A/h \geq 1.36$, Figures 10f and 10g), the liquid impacts the bottom of the tank before
31 the tank reaches its minimum stroke position. Consequently, a secondary self-intersecting clock-wise loop is formed
32 in the third quadrant. This feature can be attributed a positive (non-dissipative) energy contribution to the system.
33 This effect arises from a short-term agreement between the velocity of the tank and the orientation of the sloshing
34 force. Specifically, following the impact with the top of the tank, the liquid is thrown onto a ballistic trajectory
35 downwards. The speed of the tank is large enough such that, within the travel distance available, the liquid has the
36 time to reach to bottom of the tank and impact it before the tank reaches its minimum position, contributing thus

to its downward motion instead of impeding it and consequently reducing the overall damping or energy dissipation balance in the system. The impact with the bottom of the tank thus contributes less to the sloshing-induced damping as A/h increases. This in turn leads to the large amplitude behaviour observed in Figure 6a, where the rate of increase in the dimensional energy dissipated per cycle with respect to amplitude is *reduced* and a quadratic term needs to be introduced to form the red dashed curves.

Secondary sloshing force peaks appear at large tank accelerations (e.g. Figure 10b, $A/h = 0.45$, $f \geq 7.3$ Hz) in quadrants two and four and their origin is not immediately obvious. Similar peak-twinning has been previously observed in lower amplitude liquid sloshing involving lateral slamming with vertical walls.

Figure 10: Sloshing hysteresis cycles for various frequencies at the same tank amplitude, $h = 37.5$ mm

Figure 10: (continued): Sloshing hysteresis cycles for various frequencies at the same tank amplitude, $h = 37.5$ mm

For instance, Peregrine [23] describes two pressure peaks when liquid hits a wall laterally: the first caused by the initial impact itself and, following the liquid's upward deflection on the side wall, the second peak is caused by the liquid falling back down, a higher pressure being needed to support the liquid deceleration. Collagrossi et al. [24] further confirmed Peregrine's findings experimentally and numerically. In this work, we propose a new mechanism that explains the appearance of a secondary sloshing force peak in vertically-interacting systems. To this end, an in-depth analysis is developed here based on the mean location of the liquid inside the tank and its velocity relative to the tank.

Selected frequency-amplitude combination cases are considered among the ones shown in Figure 10 for further analysis. The selected cases span the frequency range between 4.3 Hz and 10.3 Hz, as well as the amplitude range of

0.32 to 1.00 A/h. The highest amplitudes for which video footage for visual cycle analysis was available were selected. The hysteresis cycles are studied in conjunction with the observed liquid motion (averaged liquid bulk velocity v_m^z and liquid position relative to tank – see Sections 2.1 and 2.2) in order to correlate the liquid behaviour with the measure tank response. This analysis is especially useful for future developments of equivalent mechanical models (EMMs) and reduced order models (ROMs).

Figures 11 to 18 show the mean hysteresis cycles for the maximum A/h available at the selected frequencies for the $h = 50$ mm tank. In subfigures (a), four events or instants of interest are marked, identifying the sloshing force peaks throughout the cycle. Subfigures (b) show the sloshing force as a function of time, together with the averaged liquid bulk velocity v_m^z introduced in Section 2.2. Each figure is accompanied by snapshots of each designated instant of interest showing: the mean liquid velocity field relative to the tank (black arrows); the average standard deviation of the pixel intensity indicative of the average liquid location (background colour), determined according to the methodology presented in Section 2.1; and the flow streamlines (red curves) computed as discussed in Section 2.2. Further technical details about the way these data were obtained and processed are presented in Section 2.

A series of observations can be made regarding the general patterns of the liquid-structure interaction for all of the cases presented here. Points B represent the regions where the liquid acts against the bottom of the tank. The sloshing force peaks around B and is negative, as it acts in the downwards direction. At points D the liquid impacts the top of the tank, the force being positive upwards. The position of the liquid relative to the tank can be seen in the accompanying snapshots in the form of the pixel intensity standard deviation. The low standard deviation values (blue) indicate the regions of the liquid, while the higher values (yellow) indicate the turbulent regions constituted predominantly by the liquid surfaces.

Figure 11: Force – displacement hysteresis cycles and mean vertical liquid velocity vs time for $f = 10.3$ Hz and $A/h = 0.32$

Figure 12: Average liquid position and velocity relative to tank for the points of interest presented in Figure 11

Figure 13: Force – displacement hysteresis cycles and mean vertical liquid velocity vs time for $f = 8.3$ Hz and $A/h = 0.49$

Figure 14: Average liquid position and velocity relative to tank for the points of interest presented in Figure 13

Figure 15: Force – displacement hysteresis cycles and mean vertical liquid velocity vs time for $f = 6.3$ Hz and $A/h = 0.79$

Figure 16: Average liquid position and velocity relative to tank for the points of interest presented in Figure 15

Figure 17: Force – displacement hysteresis cycles and mean vertical liquid velocity vs time for $f = 4.3$ Hz and $A/h = 1.00$

Figure 18: Average liquid position and velocity relative to tank for the points of interest presented in Figure 17

The position of the liquid is thus seen to correspond with the sloshing force at points B and D: distributed towards the top of the tank in points D and towards the bottom in points B. Of course, this effect is better seen in point B, since the liquid is aided by gravity when it hits the bottom of the tank. After the liquid impacts the tank, it rebounds. Let us first consider the bottom impacts. The velocity of the liquid increases following the impact with the tank, as it changes direction of motion; for example, this is seen Figure 11b immediately after point B, and in the corresponding subfigures for all the other cases. Following the rebound of the liquid, as the tank goes upwards, the liquid starts to push against the bottom of the tank the second time, creating a new interactional activity against the upwards motion of the tank. This effect causes the averaged liquid bulk velocity v_m^z to be constant between points B and C and, subsequently, the recovered sloshing force features a second peak at point C. The interactional mechanism is similar for the impact with the top of the tank and the argument is the same between points D and A. The second hit effect is less noticeable in the ceiling interaction case, as it is not aided by the gravitational acceleration and the net inertial effect of the liquid against the tank is less evident. This argument is further supported by the average location of the liquid for points C (mostly bottom of the tank) and A (top of the tank), as seen in Figures 12 to 18.

Finally, a global view of the hysteresis cycles for all frequencies and amplitudes of excitation can be obtained in the form of sloshing response surfaces. Figure 19 shows the sloshing force versus normalized tank amplitude and velocity for all frequencies. Each cycle corresponds to one amplitude of excitation (one harmonic excitation test case). Moving from lower to higher frequencies, the maximum values of F_S increase and the input parameter range decreases, as also observed before (e.g. Figure 10). Each collection of curves forms a sloshing response surface at a single frequency, which change their shape and curvature as the liquid interaction with the top and bottom of the tank increases in intensity. The cycles are continuously coloured here by the value of $F_S \cdot v$, the product between the sloshing force and tank velocity, which represents the instantaneous power associated with the sloshing activity. This is the power that flows or is exchanged at the structure-fluid interface, in an integral sense, in the vertical direction and is indicative of the motion opposing character of the sloshing medium. Given the adopted sign convention, it will be negative when the sloshing force acts in opposition to the velocity of the tank (i.e. tank motion opposing effect), and positive otherwise (i.e. tank motion stimulating effect). The negative sign thus implies the expected motion damping conditions whilst the positive sign identifies the atypical conditions where the integral action of the sloshing fluid acts in unison with the moving structure. The shades of red are associated with the positive power

Figure 19: Sloshing force versus normalized tank displacement and velocity for multiple frequencies of excitation. The curves are coloured by the value of sloshing force multiplied by tank velocity

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3 values with the maximum of 0.6W and the green tones imply the negative power with the minimum at -1.8W. With
4 the sloshing power being distributed unevenly in the tank's amplitude-velocity domain, it can be seen that not all parts
5 of the sloshing cycle contribute qualitatively and quantitatively equally to the overall energy measure which integrates
6 these instantaneous contributions across one full input motion cycle. The red regions are not contributing beneficially
7 to the net sloshing induced damping and correspond to the force-displacement hysteresis subcycle formations noted
8 previously (e.g. Figure 10f and 10g). This in turn contributes to the dimensional energy dissipation downwards
9 deviation from the linearity at the large excitation amplitudes (Figure 6a).

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11 We have demonstrated the global dissipative trends induced by violent vertical liquid sloshing on a range of
12 frequencies and amplitudes of excitation, as shown in Figure 6. The dissipative energy closely follows parabolic
13 trends which overlap in non-dimensional form for certain frequencies of excitation, showing significant decay that is
14 similar to what is found in the particle impact damping literature. The B-H model helped establish kinematics-based
15 reasons for the observed trends, the kinematics conditions for an increased number of liquid-tank impacts inside
16 one tank cycle being necessary for damping maximization. In-depth hysteresis cycle analysis correlated with image
17 processing techniques revealed the liquid-structure interaction reasons behind the observed trends and explained the
18 parabolic decreasing tendency of the dimensional form of the dissipative energy at large amplitudes.

28 4. Conclusions

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30 A comprehensive experimental characterization of the sloshing-induced damping due to vertical interactions was
31 presented considering both amplitude and frequency of excitation. This work builds upon previously presented exper-
32 imental cases [1, 3] and leads to sloshing-induced dissipative maps in the frequency-amplitude domain. Amplitudes of
33 excitation of 1.57 tank heights were achieved while also keeping the tank dimensions large enough such that effects
34 like surface tension do not significantly influence the flow regime. The main findings of this work may be summarized
35 as follows:
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- 37 • The energy dissipated per tank cycle was shown to follow two different parabolic trends depending on the
38 amplitude of excitation, the focus in this work being placed on the larger amplitudes range. In non-dimensional
39 form, the dissipative energy trends were shown to significantly overlap for certain frequencies of excitation. A
40 series of regression models were used to quantify the amount of overlap, E_c being described by a single function
41 across the entire frequency range between 5.3 to 10.3 Hz.
- 42 • A kinematics model based on a ballistic-harmonic formulation of the vertical trajectory of a ball between two
43 walls was employed in this work, revealing the reasons behind the experimentally observed dissipative trends.
44 It was shown that if the excitation conditions are such that impacts between the ball and the walls happen two
45 times per tank cycle, the dissipated energy is maximized. This trend closely follows the experimental dissipation
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- A localised analysis was conducted based on sloshing force-displacement hysteresis cycles to gain further insight into the global dissipation trends. The shape of the hysteresis cycles show common features across multiple amplitudes and frequencies of excitation and are directly caused by observed interactions between the liquid and the tank. A statistical approach was taken in which all quantities (liquid location, velocity, sloshing force) were observed for a large number of oscillations and then averaged, allowing the identification of persistent trends of motion and interactions. A procedure based on pixel intensity standard deviation was employed based on high-speed video footage, allowing measurement of the averaged liquid location relative to the tank. The liquid velocity was estimated using optical flow which, together with the liquid location and the measured tank force and acceleration, allowed for a comprehensive description of the kinematics and dynamics of the system. Based on this information it was shown how the liquid motion relative to the tank generates the observed hysteresis cycles and, consequently, induced damping. The observed global trend of parabolic deviation from the linear increase in dimensional dissipated energy per cycle with increasing amplitude was explained based on the formation of hysteresis sub-cycles that add energy to the system.

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These conclusions lead to a better fundamental understanding of the vertical violent sloshing interaction and induced damping. Moreover, the observed global trends together with the localised hysteresis cycle analysis have the capability of aiding future developments in equivalent mechanical models and reduced order models with applications in, but not limited to, aerospace engineering.

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References

- [1] L. Constantin, J. De Courcy, B. Titurus, T. Rendall, J. Cooper, Analysis of damping from vertical sloshing in a sdof system, *Mechanical Systems and Signal Processing* 152 (2021) 107452. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ymssp.2020.107452>.
- [2] J. Martinez-Carrascal, L. González-Gutiérrez, Experimental study of the liquid damping effects on a sdof vertical sloshing tank, *Journal of Fluids and Structures* 100 (2021) 103172. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfluidstructs.2020.103172>.
- [3] L. Constantin, J. De Courcy, B. Titurus, T. Rendall, J. Cooper, Sloshing induced damping across froude numbers in a harmonically vertically excited system, *Journal of Sound and Vibration* 510 (2021) 116302. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2021.116302>.
- [4] R. A. Ibrahim, *Liquid Sloshing Dynamics: Theory and Applications*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge, 2005. doi:10.1017/CBO9780511536656.
- [5] R. G. Cook, D. E. Calderon, J. E. Cooper, M. H. Lowenberg, S. A. Neild, Industrially inspired gust loads analysis of various-aspect-ratio wings featuring geometric nonlinearity, *Journal of Aircraft* 57 (1) (2020) 13–28. doi:10.2514/1.C035294.
- [6] L. R. Jenkinson, P. Simpkin, D. Rhodes, *Civil jet aircraft design*, Butterworth-Heinemann, London, 1999.
- [7] APS Dynamics, APS 113 ELECTRO-SEIS, Brochure, accessed 04.10.2022, URL: tinyurl.com/ybdarj6f (2022).

- 1
2
3
4 [8] L. Constantin, J. J. D. Courcy, B. Titurus, T. C. S. Rendall, J. E. Cooper, Statistical analysis of sloshing-induced dissipative energy across
5 a range of froude numbers, *IOP Conference Series: Materials Science and Engineering* 1226 (1) (2022) 012040. doi:10.1088/1757-
6 899x/1226/1/012040.
- 7 [9] A. Masullo, R. Theunissen, Automated mask generation for piv image analysis based on pixel intensity statistics, *Exp Fluids* 58 (2017).
8 doi:10.1007/s00348-017-2357-3.
- 9
10 [10] L. Constantin, J. J. De Courcy, B. Titurus, T. C. S. Rendall, J. E. Cooper, Sloshing fluid-structure interaction and induced damping effects:
11 modelling and experimental analysis, in: *In Proc. International Conference on Noise and Vibration Engineering ISMA*, Leuven, Belgium,
12 2020.
- 13 [11] B. K. Horn, B. G. Schunck, Determining optical flow, *Artificial Intelligence* 17 (1) (1981) 185–203. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/0004-
14 3702(81)90024-2.
- 15 [12] Z. Tu, W. Xie, D. Zhang, R. Poppe, R. C. Veltkamp, B. Li, J. Yuan, A survey of variational and cnn-based optical flow techniques, *Signal*
16 *Processing: Image Communication* 72 (2019) 9–24. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.image.2018.12.002.
- 17 [13] I. Kajo, A. S. Malik, N. Kamel, An evaluation of optical flow algorithms for crowd analytics in surveillance system, in: *2016 6th International*
18 *Conference on Intelligent and Advanced Systems (ICIAS)*, 2016, pp. 1–6. doi:10.1109/ICIAS.2016.7824064.
- 19 [14] F. Bonin-Font, A. Ortiz, G. Oliver, Visual navigation for mobile robots: A survey, *Journal of Intelligent & Robotic Systems* 53 (2008)
20 263–296. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/s10846-008-9235-4.
- 21 [15] C. Marzban, S. Sandgathe, Optical flow for verification, *Weather and Forecasting* 25 (5) (2010) 1479 – 1494.
22 doi:10.1175/2010WAF2222351.1.
- 23 [16] Y. Arosquipa Nina, R. Shi, D. Wüthrich, H. Chanson, Intrusive and non-intrusive two-phase air-water measurements on stepped spillways: A
24 physical study, *Experimental Thermal and Fluid Science* 131 (2022) 110545. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.expthermflusci.2021.110545.
- 25 [17] Y. Song, K. Chang, Y. Ryu, S. Kwon, Experimental study on flow kinematics and impact pressure in liquid sloshing, *Exp Fluids* 54 (2013).
26 doi:10.1007/s00348-013-1592-5.
- 27 [18] Y. Ryu, K.-A. Chang, H.-J. Lim, Use of bubble image velocimetry for measurement of plunging wave impinging on structure and associated
28 greenwater, *Measurement Science and Technology* 16 (10) (2005) 1945–1953. doi:10.1088/0957-0233/16/10/009.
- 29 [19] N. Cavalagli, C. Biscarini, A. L. Facci, F. Ubertini, S. Ubertini, Experimental and numerical analysis of energy dissipation in a sloshing
30 absorber, *Journal of Fluids and Structures* 68 (2017) 466–481. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfluidstructs.2016.11.020.
- 31 [20] F. Saltari, M. Pizzoli, G. Coppotelli, F. Gambioli, J. E. Cooper, F. Mastroddi, Experimental characterisation of slosh-
32 ing tank dissipative behaviour in vertical harmonic excitation, *Journal of Fluids and Structures* 109 (2022) 103478.
33 doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfluidstructs.2021.103478.
- 34 [21] R. Friend, V. Kinra, Particle impact damping, *Journal of Sound and Vibration* 233 (1) (2000) 93–118.
35 doi:https://doi.org/10.1006/jsvi.1999.2795.
- 36 [22] R. Ruiz, A. Taflanidis, D. Lopez-Garcia, Characterization and design of tuned liquid dampers with floating roof considering arbitrary tank
37 cross-sections, *Journal of Sound and Vibration* 368 (2016) 36–54. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jsv.2016.01.014.
- 38 [23] D. H. Peregrine, Water-wave impact on walls, *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics* 35 (1) (2003) 23–43.
39 doi:10.1146/annurev.fluid.35.101101.161153.
- 40 [24] A. Colagrossi, F. Palladino, M. Greco, Experimental and numerical investigation of 2d sloshing with slamming, in: *In Proc. 19th International*
41 *Workshop on Water Waves and Floating Body*, 2004.
- 42
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44
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Highlights

Nonlinear damping effects in vertically vibrating systems with violently sloshing liquid

L. Constantin, J. De Courcy, B. Titurus, T.C.S Rendall, J.E.Cooper

- Nonlinear damping effects due to vertical sloshing are studied
- Dissipative trends across a large range of amplitudes and frequencies are shown
- A ballistic model explains the kinematics-based reasons behind the observed trends

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